

LIFE CALLIOPE

LIFE17 NAT/IT/000565 "CALLIOPE"
COASTAL DUNE HABITATS,
SUBLITTORAL SANDBANK, MARINE REEFS:
CONSERVATION, PROTECTION, AND THREATS MITIGATION

UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI
DEL MOLISE

Le buone pratiche del Progetto LIFE CALLIOPE The best practices of the LIFE CALLIOPE Project Layman's Report

ITALY, ABRUZZO REGION

SAC IT7120215 Torre del Cerrano

pSCI Ripari di Giobbe – Foce del Fiume Foro

pSCI Punta dell'Acquabella – Foce del Fiume Moro

SAC IT7140107 Lecceta di Torino di Sangro - Foce del Fiume Sangro

SAC IT7140108 Punta Aderci – Punta della Penna

SAC IT7140109 Marina di Vasto

CYPRUS

SAC CY4000001 Periochi Polis - Gialia

- LIFE CALLIOPE (Coastal dune habitats, sublittoral sandbanks, marine reefs: conservation, protection, and threats mitigation - LIFE 17 NAT/IT/000565) è un progetto finanziato dalla Comunità Europea per proteggere i fragili ecosistemi costieri dunali e marini e mitigare gli impatti prodotti dalle attività dell'uomo lungo il litorale abruzzese in Italia, e lungo le coste nord-occidentali di Cipro.

- Queste aree, infatti, vengono spesso trasformate dalle attività antropiche che danneggiano la biodiversità delle dune, dei fondali sabbiosi e rocciosi. Tra le modifiche indotte dall'uomo, si osservano lo spianamento e la cementificazione delle aree dunali, il degrado degli ambienti naturali, e, in mare, il prelievo eccessivo di pescato e l'uso di metodi distruttivi per la pesca nei fondali e nelle scogliere.

- Per la salvaguardia di questi preziosi ambienti è necessario adottare buone pratiche che consentano di preservare il patrimonio naturalistico e la bellezza dei paesaggi costieri. Localizzazione: Siti della rete Natura 2000. ZSC IT7120215 Torre del Cerrano, pSIC Ripari di Giobbe – Foce del Fiume Foro, pSIC Punta dell'Acquabella – Foce del Fiume Moro, ZSC IT7140107 Lecceta litoranea di Torino di Sangro e Foce del Fiume Sangro, ZSC IT7140108 Punta Aderci - Punta della Penna, ZSC IT7140109 Marina di Vasto (Italia), ZSC CY4000001 Periochi Polis - Gialia (Cipro).

- LIFE CALLIOPE (Coastal dune habitats, sublittoral sandbanks, marine reefs: Conservation, Protection, and Threats Mitigation - LIFE 17 NAT/IT/000565) is a project funded by the European Community to protect fragile coastal dune and marine ecosystems and mitigate the impacts of human activities along the Abruzzo coastline in Italy, and the northwestern coasts of Cyprus.

- These areas are often altered by human activities that damage the biodiversity of dunes, sandy and rocky seabeds. Among the changes induced by humans are the leveling and cementing of dune areas, degradation of natural environments, excessive fishing and the use of destructive methods in seabeds and cliffs.

- To safeguard these precious environments, it is necessary to adopt good practices that allow for the preservation of natural heritage and the beauty of coastal landscapes.

Localization: Sites of the Natura 2000 network. SAC IT7120215 Torre del Cerrano, pSCI Ripari di Giobbe – Foce del Fiume Foro, pSCI Punta dell'Acquabella – Foce del Fiume Moro, SAC IT7140107 Lecceta litoranea di Torino di Sangro e Foce del Fiume Sangro, SAC IT7140108 Punta Aderci - Punta della Penna, SAC IT7140109 Marina di Vasto (Italy), SAC CY4000001 Periochi Polis - Gialia (Cyprus).

Gli obiettivi del progetto sono stati:

1. Il recupero e la valorizzazione degli habitat di interesse comunitario nei siti Natura 2000 coinvolti nel progetto.
2. L'istituzione di nuovi siti costieri della rete Natura 2000 e l'ampliamento a mare di siti.
3. Lo studio dell'impatto socio-economico del progetto.
4. La sensibilizzazione del pubblico sui temi ambientali.

The objectives of the project were:

1. Recovery and enhancement of the habitats of community interest within the Natura 2000 sites involved in the project.
2. Establishment of new coastal sites within the Natura 2000 network and the extension of existing sites into marine areas.
3. Study of the socio-economic impact of the project.
4. Public awareness raising on environmental issues.

Gli ambienti dunali

Le dune costiere sabbiose sono ecosistemi molto particolari dal punto di vista ecologico, biologico e paesaggistico. Le condizioni di vita molto difficili (vento, sale, substrato instabile) fanno sì che si possano trovare piante e animali altamente specializzati. Le dune sabbiose forniscono importanti servizi ecosistemici, tra cui il mantenimento di habitat per una biodiversità minacciata, la protezione delle aree retrodunali dagli effetti del vento e del sale, il contrasto dell'erosione costiera, l'attrattività per molte attività ricreative e la balneazione.

Coastal Dune Environments

Sandy coastal dunes are very unique ecosystems from an ecological, biological, and landscape perspective. The challenging living conditions (wind, salt, unstable substrate) result in the presence of highly specialized plants and animals. Sandy dunes provide important ecosystem services, such as maintaining habitats for threatened biodiversity, protecting the interdunal areas from the effects of wind and salt, countering coastal erosion, and offering tourist appeal related to swimming and other recreational activities.

Gli ambienti sommersi sabbiosi

Sono i fondali sabbiosi con vegetazione sparsa rappresentata da alcune alghe e dalla pianta sottomarina *Cymodocea nodosa*. Essi ospitano specie quali il cavalluccio marino (*Hippocampus hippocampus*), bivalvi come *Chamelea gallina* e *Lentidium mediterraneum*, gasteropodi come *Aporrhais pespelecani* e echinodermi come le stelle marine.

The Sandy Submerged Environments

Seabeds with sparse vegetation represented by some algae and the underwater plant *Cymodocea nodosa*. They host species such as the seahorse (*Hippocampus hippocampus*), bivalves like *Chamelea gallina* and *Lentidium mediterraneum*, gastropods like *Aporrhais pespelecani*, and echinoderms like starfish.

Gli ambienti di scogliera

Il territorio costiero della costa abruzzese è rappresentato nella parte meridionale da falesie che sprofondano in mare creando scogliere sommerse ricche di biodiversità. Alcune rocce sono formate da concrezioni e incrostazioni di coralli, vermi e bivalvi vivi o morti. Molte sono anche le alghe con presenza di nudibranchi, crostacei e pesci.

The Reef Environments

The coastal territory of the Abruzzo coast is characterized in the southern part by cliffs that plunge into the sea, creating submerged reefs rich in biodiversity. Some rocks are formed by concretions and encrustations of corals, worms, and bivalves, both living and dead. There are also many algae, with the presence of nudibranchs, crustaceans, and fish.

Habitat e specie target

Habitat and target species

Vegetazione rada della spiaggia
1210: Vegetazione annua delle linee
di deposito marine: formazioni erbacee, annuali

Sparse vegetation of the beach
1210: Annual vegetation of marine deposit lines:
herbaceous, annual formations

Vegetazione del piede delle dune
2110: Dune embrionali mobili

Vegetation of the dune foot
2110: Shifting embryonic dunes

Vegetazione delle dune - 2120: Dune mobili del cordone
litorale con presenza di *Ammophila arenaria* (dune bianche)

Vegetation of the dunes - 2120: Shifting coastal dunes
with the presence of *Ammophila arenaria* (white dunes)

Vegetazione delle radure dunali
2230: Dune con prati de *Malcolmietalia*

Vegetation of the dune clearings
2230: Dunes with grasslands of *Malcolmietalia*

Macchia mediterranea con ginepri
2250*: Dune costiere con *Juniperus* spp.

Mediterranean scrub with junipers
2250*: Coastal dunes with *Juniperus* spp.

Vegetazione degli ambienti umidi retrodunali
1410: Pascoli inondati mediterranei
(*Juncetalia maritimi*)

Vegetation of humid interdunal environments
1410: Mediterranean salt meadows
(*Juncetalia maritimi*)

Testuggine di Hermann - Hermann's Tortoise (*Testudo hermanni* Gmelin , 1789)

Tra le tre specie di testuggini terrestri presenti in Italia *Testudo hermanni* è considerata maggiormente a rischio a livello nazionale. La distribuzione della specie nella penisola Italiana ha subito una lenta e continua contrazione a causa della progressiva riduzione, frammentazione e degrado di habitat naturali e semi-naturali idonei alla sua conservazione; ad oggi è considerata specie "vulnerabile" nella Lista Rossa IUCN dei Vertebrati Italiani; è quindi sottoposta a diversi regimi di tutela.

Among the three species of terrestrial tortoises present in Italy *Testudo hermanni* is considered the most at risk at the national level. The distribution of the species in the Italian peninsula has undergone a slow and continuous contraction due to the progressive reduction, fragmentation, and degradation of natural and semi-natural habitats suitable for its conservation. Today, it is considered a species "vulnerable" in the IUCN Red List of Italian Vertebrates; it is therefore subject to various protection regimes.

Dattero di mare - Date Mussel *Lithophaga lithophaga* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Il dattero di mare ha una crescita di pochi millimetri l'anno e colonizza interamente le cavità poco illuminate delle scogliere anche a bassa profondità. La sua presenza modifica la roccia e permette la colonizzazione di tante altre specie marine che altrimenti non riuscirebbero ad attecchire sulla roccia nuda. La pesca e il consumo del dattero di mare è illegale poiché per prelevare gli individui è necessario frantumare interamente la roccia che li ospita, con gravissimi danni all'habitat di scogliera.

The Date Mussel has a growth rate of a few millimeters per year. It entirely colonizes the poorly lit cavities of cliffs, even at shallow depths. Its presence modifies the rock and allows the colonization of many other marine species that would otherwise be unable to establish themselves on bare rock. The fishing and consumption of the date mussel are illegal because extracting the individuals requires completely breaking the rock that hosts them, causing severe damage to the cliff habitat.

***Maresia nana var. glabra* (Meikle) Christodoulou & Hand**

Maresia nana var. glabra è una varietà endemica di Cipro, presente solo nel sito target e in nessun'altra parte del mondo. È una pianta annuale, con piccoli fiori color malva. Ha foglie e fusti glabri in contrasto con le piante con peli stellati della specie più diffusa. Il suo stato di conservazione è valutato come in pericolo critico in base ai criteri della IUCN e pertanto inclusa nel Red Data Book della Flora di Cipro.

Maresia nana var. glabra is a Cyprus endemic variety, found only at the target site and nowhere else in the world. It is annual, with small, mauve flowers. It has smooth leaves and stems, in contrast to the more widespread species that have stellate hairs. Its conservation status is evaluated as Critically Endangered based on the criteria of IUCN, and included in the Red Data Book of the Flora of Cyprus.

Gli studi preliminari e il loro valore per lo svolgimento del progetto

Preliminary studies and their value for project implementation

Grazie agli studi e alle indagini condotte nella fase preliminare del progetto ad opera dei ricercatori delle due università coinvolte, è stato possibile definire e cartografare in dettaglio la distribuzione degli habitat e delle specie di valore conservazionistico e valutare il loro stato di conservazione.

Questi dati sono serviti poi come base per la valutazione, durante lo svolgimento del progetto, dell'efficacia di quanto realizzato, misurando i benefici sugli habitat e le specie target. Queste informazioni saranno fondamentali per orientare le misure di conservazione e di gestione degli ambienti costieri e marini nei territori coinvolti nel progetto LIFE CALLIOPE.

Thanks to the studies and investigations conducted during the preliminary phase of the project by researchers from the two universities involved, it was possible to accurately define and map the distribution of habitats and species of conservation value and assess their conservation status in detail. These data then served as a basis for evaluating, during the project implementation, the effectiveness of the actions taken, measuring the benefits to the target habitats and species. This information will be crucial for guiding conservation and management measures for coastal and marine environments in the areas involved in the LIFE CALLIOPE project.

Gli interventi di ripristino e protezione ambientale

La protezione degli habitat dunali

Environmental Restoration and Protection Interventions

The protection of dune habitats

Il calpestio e il consumo di suolo rappresentano una grave minaccia per la conservazione delle dune in quanto causano il degrado degli habitat e il declino della biodiversità. Per affrontare questo problema, il progetto ha previsto la realizzazione di diverse strutture a protezione di circa 22 ettari di habitat dunali: a) 240 metri lineari di passerelle pedonali che attraversano la duna dall'entroterra verso la spiaggia; b) 2344 metri di paletti e cordino per delimitare le dune ed evitarne il calpestio; c) 1 sbarra di accesso per impedire l'ingresso dei veicoli a motore fino alla duna; d) 60 metri lineari di gabbioni come dissuasori per l'accesso dei veicoli sulla spiaggia. Sono stati inoltre affissi 17 pannelli che hanno la finalità di informare i fruitori della spiaggia sui benefici ambientali generati dalle attività del progetto, nonché di fornire informazioni sulla biodiversità locale.

Trampling and land consumption represent a serious threat to the conservation of dunes as they cause habitat degradation and a decline in biodiversity. To address this issue, the project includes the construction of various structures to protect approximately 22 hectares of dune habitats: a) 240 linear meters of pedestrian walkways that cross the dunes from the inland to the beach; b) 2344 meters of posts and rope to delimit the dunes and prevent trampling; c) 1 access barrier to prevent motor vehicles from entering the dunes; d) 60 linear meters of gabions to deter vehicle access to the beach. Additionally, 17 panels have been installed to inform beachgoers about the environmental.

Gli interventi di ripristino e protezione ambientale La propagazione delle specie native

Environmental Restoration and Protection Interventions The propagation of native species

Il ripristino della vegetazione dunale attraverso la piantumazione di specie native è cruciale per restituire agli ambienti costieri sabbiosi degradati il loro ecosistema originario. I ricercatori dell'Università degli Studi del Molise hanno raccolto semi e talee delle specie native dunali e le hanno coltivate con il supporto del Vivaio Forestale Regionale "Le Marinelle" di Marina di Petacciato in Italia e il Vivaio dell'Università Frederick a Cipro. L'Università del Molise, in collaborazione col Vivaio Forestale, ha inoltre messo a punto un corretto protocollo per ottenere la germinazione da seme delle specie dunali native, reso disponibile nel Manuale di propagazione delle specie degli ambienti dunali adriatici.

I ricercatori della Frederick University di Cipro hanno raccolto 4000 semi della specie endemica *Maresia nana var. glabra* e hanno effettuato la propagazione di questa specie, rendendola

disponibile per la messa a dimora sulle dune cipriote.

The restoration of dune vegetation through the planting of native species is crucial for returning degraded sandy coastal environments to their original ecosystems. Researchers from the University of Molise collected seeds and cuttings of native dune species and cultivated them with the support of the Regional Forest Nursery "Le Marinelle" in Marina di Petacciato, Italy, and the Nursery of Frederick University in Cyprus. The University of Molise, in collaboration with the Forest Nursery, also developed an effective protocol for obtaining germination from seeds of native dune species, which is made available in the Manual for the Propagation of Species in Adriatic Dune Environments. Researchers from Frederick University in Cyprus collected 4,000 seeds of the endemic species *Maresia nana var. glabra* and propagated this species, making it available for planting on Cypriot dunes.

Gli interventi di ripristino e protezione ambientale

La bioricostruzione delle dune

Environmental Restoration and Protection Interventions

The bio restoration of dunes

La vegetazione dunale svolge un ruolo cruciale nel consolidare il sedimento sabbioso. La sua perdita compromette l'intera zonazione dunale, accelerando l'erosione delle coste e causando danni significativi all'ambiente naturale, inclusa la perdita delle spiagge.

La ricostruzione della continuità dei sistemi di dune mobili è stata realizzata per un totale di 33 ha, prevedendo l'impianto di oltre 10.433 piantine di specie dunali native, prodotte da seme autoctono e raccolte in siti coerenti dal punto di vista geografico ed ecologico. Questo approccio ha permesso di riqualificare circa 17 ettari di habitat idoneo per la sopravvivenza e riproduzione della specie target

Testudo hermanni.

Dune vegetation plays a crucial role in stabilizing sandy sediment. Its loss compromises the entire dune zonation, accelerating coastal erosion and causing significant damage to the natural environment, including the loss of beaches. The reconstruction of the continuity of mobile dune systems was achieved over a total of 33 hectares, involving the planting of over 10,433 seedlings of native dune species, produced from locally sourced seeds collected in geographically and ecologically consistent sites. This approach has allowed for the rehabilitation of approximately 17 hectares of suitable habitat for the survival and reproduction of the target species *Testudo hermanni*.

Gli interventi di ripristino e protezione ambientale L'eradicazione delle specie aliene

Environmental Restoration and Protection Interventions The eradication of alien species

Le invasioni di specie aliene costituiscono una seria minaccia per la biodiversità globale. Nel sito costiero cipriota 'Periochi Polis - Gialia', si sono riscontrate piante di *Acacia saligna*, una specie esotica invasiva caratterizzata dalla sua elevata capacità riproduttiva e dalla sua veloce diffusione negli ambienti dunali mediterranei. La rimozione della maggior parte delle piante di acacia ha comportato la riqualificazione di circa 12,4 ettari dell'habitat 2250* (macchia a ginepri). Inoltre nello stesso luogo è avvenuta la rimozione dei rifiuti di cava, su un'area di 1,7 ettari.

Invasive alien species pose a serious threat to global biodiversity. At the coastal site 'Periochi Polis - Gialia' in Cyprus, plants of *Acacia saligna*, an exotic invasive species characterized by its high reproductive capacity and rapid spread in Mediterranean dune environments, have been found. The removal of most of the acacia plants has led to the rehabilitation of approximately 12.4 hectares of habitat 2250* (coastal dunes with *Juniperus* spp.). Additionally, in the same location, quarry waste was removed from an area of 1.7 hectares.

Gli interventi di ripristino e protezione ambientale

La realizzazione del parco boe per la protezione degli ambienti marini

Environmental Restoration and Protection Interventions

The creation of the buoy park for the protection of marine environments

In Abruzzo è stata messa sotto protezione la biodiversità delle scogliere marine e delle praterie sommerse per 347,12 ettari nei siti Natura 2000 pSCI Ripari di Giobbe – Foce del Fiume Foro, pSCI Punta dell'Acquabella – Foce del Fiume Moro, ZSC IT7140108 Punta Aderci – Punta della Penna, regolamentando l'accesso e delimitando l'area con 12 boe di segnalazione. Inoltre, l'azione ha permesso il recupero di circa 24,91 ha di superficie idonea alla sopravvivenza e riproduzione della specie target *Lithophaga lithophaga*.

In Abruzzo, the biodiversity of marine cliffs and submerged meadows has been protected over an area of 347.12 hectares within the Natura 2000 sites pSCI Ripari di Giobbe – Foce del Fiume Foro, pSCI Punta dell'Acquabella – Foce del Fiume Moro, and SAC IT7140108 Punta Aderci – Punta della Penna, by regulating access and delineating the area with 12 marker buoys. Additionally, this action has enabled the recovery of approximately 24.91 hectares of suitable habitat for the survival and reproduction of the target species *Lithophaga lithophaga*.

Piano d’Azione per la salvaguardia delle coste abruzzesi

Action Plan for the Protection of the Abruzzo Coast

Il progetto ha previsto la stesura di un Piano d’Azione Regionale Costiero per la gestione sostenibile degli ambienti naturali ancora presenti lungo tutta la costa abruzzese. L’adozione di buone pratiche di gestione delle aree dunali consentiranno di aumentare la superficie degli habitat dunali idonei alle specie bandiera: fratino (*Charadrius alexandrinus*) e testuggine terrestre (*Testudo hermanni*).

Il Piano d’Azione Regionale Costiero della Regione Abruzzo (ARCA) ha previsto la descrizione e la mappatura della vegetazione dunale nelle Zone Speciali di Conservazione della Rete Natura 2000, nelle Riserve Naturali Regionali costiere e nelle aree demaniali con habitat dunali di valore conservazionistico. Il Piano ARCA è stato condiviso con i Comuni costieri e gli Enti Gestori delle aree protette in incontri tenutosi a Pescara e Ortona (CH) in Italia.

The project included the creation of a Regional Coastal Action Plan for the sustainable management of the remaining natural environments along the entire Abruzzo coast. The adoption of good management practices for dune areas will allow the enlargement of dune habitat available for the flagship species such as the Kentish plover (*Charadrius alexandrinus*) and the Hermann’s tortoise (*Testudo hermanni*). The Regional Coastal Action Plan of the Abruzzo Region (ARCA) included the description and mapping of dune vegetation in the Special Areas of Conservation of the Natura 2000 Network, in the Regional Coastal Nature Reserves, and in public areas with dune habitats of conservation value. The ARCA Plan was shared with coastal municipalities and the managing bodies of protected areas during meetings held in Pescara and Ortona (CH), Italy.

Ampliamento della rete Natura 2000

Implementation of the Natura 2000 Network

Una delle azioni più significative del progetto è stato l'ampliamento della rete Natura 2000 con l'istituzione di due nuovi siti di interesse comunitario costa-mare a Ortona, pSIC Ripari di Giobbe – Foce del Fiume Foro e pSIC Punta dell'Acquabella – Foce del Fiume Moro, per un totale di circa 275 ha e l'ampliamento a mare del sito ZSC IT7140108 Punta Aderci – Punta della Penna, con l'aggiunta di circa 216 ha. Il progetto LIFE CALLIOPE ha permesso così la protezione degli ambienti sommersi di scogliera e di fondale sabbioso per un totale di circa 347 ha. Le aree a mare sono quelle antistanti la costa per circa 300 metri di ampiezza verso il largo che comprendono i primi 10 metri di profondità.

One of the most significant actions of the project was the expansion of the Natura 2000 network with the establishment of two new coastal-sea Sites of Community Importance (pSCI) in Ortona: Ripari di Giobbe – Foce del Fiume Foro and Punta dell'Acquabella – Foce del Fiume Moro, totaling approximately 275 hectares. Additionally, the marine extension of the Site of Community Importance (SAC) IT7140108 Punta Aderci – Punta della Penna was expanded by approximately 216 hectares. The LIFE CALLIOPE project thus enabled the protection of submerged rocky reef and sandy seabed environments totaling approximately 347 hectares. The marine areas include those adjacent to the coast for about 300 meters seaward, encompassing the first 10 meters of depth.

Il monitoraggio ecologico

The ecological monitoring

Le attività di monitoraggio degli habitat e delle specie sono state svolte in modo continuativo per i 5 anni di progetto dai ricercatori delle Università coinvolte nelle aree interessate dagli interventi di ripristino e di tutela ambientale. Per gli ambienti dunali sono state individuate 68 aree di monitoraggio della vegetazione in Italia e 8 aree a Cipro nei siti dove si sono svolti gli interventi di rinaturalizzazione. Ai fini dell'azione, per ogni area di monitoraggio è stata registrata la copertura delle specie di piante vascolari presenti. Il monitoraggio è avvenuto prima, durante e dopo l'implementazione delle azioni di conservazione (Azioni C), valutando l'impatto sugli habitat target utilizzando la ricchezza e l'abbondanza delle specie.

Per quanto riguarda le specie faunistiche, sono stati effettuati 11 transetti lineari della lunghezza di circa 1 km, trasversali alla linea di costa, per l'osservazione di rettili e 17 transetti lineari della lunghezza di circa 300 m, paralleli alla linea di costa, per il monitoraggio degli uccelli. Per gli ambienti marini sono state svolte immersioni subacquee e monitorate 10 aree.

I dati acquisiti sono stati utilizzati per l'aggiornamento dei formulari standard e della cartografia degli habitat di interesse comunitario dei siti della Rete Natura 2000 coinvolti nel progetto. Inoltre, questi siti verranno monitorati nel tempo dai ricercatori delle due Università per acquisire periodici aggiornamenti sulla biodiversità nelle aree target del progetto, anche dopo la fine del progetto.

The monitoring activities of habitats and species were carried out continuously over the five years of the project by researchers from the involved universities in the areas affected by the restoration and environmental protection interventions. For dune environments, 68 vegetation monitoring areas were identified in Italy and 8 areas in Cyprus at the sites where renaturalization interventions were carried out. The coverage of vascular plant species present was recorded for each monitoring area. Monitoring took place before, during, and after the implementation of conservation actions (Actions C), evaluating the impact on the target habitats by using species richness and abundance.

Regarding faunal species, 11 linear transects approximately 1 km long, transverse to the coastline, were conducted for reptile observation, and 17 linear transects approximately 300 m long, parallel to the coastline, were conducted for bird monitoring. For marine environments, scuba diving surveys were conducted, and 10 areas were monitored.

The acquired data were used to update the standard forms and habitat maps of the community interest sites of the Natura 2000 Network involved in the project. Additionally, these sites will be monitored over time by researchers from the two universities to periodically update biodiversity information in the project's target areas, even after the project's conclusion.

Impatto socio-economico del progetto

Socio-economic Impact of the Project

L'obiettivo dell'Azione è stato quello di valutare gli impatti sociali ed economici degli interventi realizzati dal Progetto LIFE CALLIOPE. A tal fine sono stati individuati i potenziali impatti sulla dimensione economica (micro e macro) e sulla scala territoriale (locale e globale). Per indagare la dimensione economica sono stati selezionati indicatori utili a valutare le esternalità sia su Enti e stakeholders che operano sul territorio (micro) sia sulla collettività e cittadini in generale (macro). Per quanto riguarda la scala territoriale, sono stati considerati i possibili impatti sui singoli siti (locale) ma anche a scala più ampia come, ad esempio, il livello regionale e nazionale (globale). Nell'analisi un ruolo attivo è stato svolto dagli stakeholders pubblici e privati e dalla comunità locale coinvolta in un'indagine per valutare il miglioramento del benessere sociale ed ambientale, generato dagli interventi di progetto. A tal fine sono stati selezionati e contattati più di 250 operatori nel settore turistico ricettivo e 30 stakeholders pubblici (es. Enti Locali) e privati (es. cittadini).

The objective of the Action was to assess the social and economic impacts of the interventions carried out by the LIFE CALLIOPE Project. To this end, potential impacts on both the economic dimension (micro and macro) and the territorial scale (local and global) were identified. To investigate the economic dimension, indicators were selected to assess externalities on both entities and stakeholders operating in the territory (micro) and on the community and citizens in general (macro). Regarding the territorial scale, possible impacts on individual sites (local) were considered, as well as on a broader scale such as the regional and national levels (global). In the analysis, an active role was played by public and private stakeholders and the local community involved in a survey to evaluate the improvement of social and environmental well being generated by project interventions. To this end, more than 250 operators in the tourism sector and 30 public (e.g., local authorities) and private stakeholders (e.g., citizens) were selected and contacted.

Valutazione dei servizi ecosistemici

Assessment of Ecosystem Services

Nell'ambito di questa azione sono stati valutati i benefici ambientali ed economici offerti dai Siti Natura 2000 ed il bacino di utenza rappresentato dai consumatori finali. A tal fine sono state identificate e implementate metodologie di quantificazione biofisica e valutazione economica di quattro servizi ecosistemici: Habitat per la biodiversità, Protezione dall'erosione, Sequestro di carbonio e Valore ricreativo. Il valore complessivo stimato per questi servizi ecosistemici supera gli 8 milioni di euro con una media di circa 1.400 euro ad ettaro. Oltre alla popolazione residente i principali beneficiari sono rappresentati dai turisti. Inoltre, le azioni di conservazione adottate proteggono le infrastrutture esposte al rischio di erosione costiera come, ad esempio, stabilimenti balneari, porti e attività commerciali.

Within this action, the environmental and economic benefits offered by the Natura 2000 Sites and the user base represented by end-consumers were evaluated. To this end, methodologies for the quantification of biophysical and economic assessment of four ecosystem services were identified and implemented: Biodiversity Habitat, Erosion Protection, Carbon Sequestration, and Recreational Value. The overall estimated value for these ecosystem services exceeds 8 million euros, with an average of approximately 1,400 euros per hectare. In addition to the resident population, the main beneficiaries are tourists. Furthermore, the conservation actions taken protect the infrastructure exposed to the risk of coastal erosion, such as beach resorts, ports, and commercial activities.

Comunicazione e sensibilizzazione

Communication and Awareness

Le azioni di conservazione sono state affiancate da numerose attività di comunicazione, sensibilizzazione e coinvolgimento di studenti, residenti, turisti e operatori locali al fine di far conoscere il patrimonio naturalistico e le problematiche ambientali della costa abruzzese e cipriota. Sono stati realizzati depliant e opuscoli informativi, pannelli esplicativi collocati nelle aree di intervento, documenti audiovisivi (4 minivideo ed 2 documentari) di progetto, rollup tematici e una newsletter periodica sulle attività del progetto, una ogni anno per un totale di 5. Sono stati anche realizzati comunicati stampa ed interviste pubblicate dalla stampa locale. Sono state coinvolte 21 scuole con lezioni in classe e visite guidate, compatibilmente con le restrizioni dovute alla pandemia da Covid-19, che hanno interessato circa 1500 ragazzi. Il sito web, in italiano e inglese, e la pagina Facebook del progetto sono stati gli strumenti per far conoscere il progetto e lo stato di avanzamento delle attività nel tempo, attraverso, ad esempio, le news mensili e la rassegna stampa, la divulgazione per i tavoli di concertazione, le conferenze, gli eventi informativi e di educazione ambientale.

Conservation actions were accompanied by numerous communication, awareness, and engagement activities involving students, residents, tourists, and local operators to raise awareness about the natural heritage and environmental issues of the Abruzzo and Cypriot coasts. Information brochures, leaflets, explanatory panels placed in intervention areas, audiovisual documents (4 clips and 2 documentary), thematic rollup and a periodic newsletter on project activities were produced once a year for a total of 5. Press releases and interviews published by the local media were also conducted. Twenty-one schools were involved with classroom lessons and tours, consistent with restrictions due to the Covid-19 pandemic, involving about 1,500 children. The project's website, available in Italian and English, and its Facebook page served as tools to disseminate information about the project and the progress of activities over time. Monthly news updates, press reviews, dissemination for consultation meetings, conferences, informational events, and environmental education were some of the methods used to engage with the community.

Prospettive future Future Perspectives

Guardando al futuro del progetto, è previsto un coinvolgimento continuo delle Università nel monitoraggio e nella valutazione dell'efficacia delle azioni di conservazione. Inoltre, si prevede che gli enti locali, incaricati della manutenzione delle opere realizzate, giocheranno un ruolo fondamentale nel garantire la continuità e il successo delle iniziative di protezione e gestione sostenibile degli ambienti costieri e marini. I portatori di interesse saranno chiamati a contribuire attivamente con il loro supporto e le loro risorse per assicurare il mantenimento e lo sviluppo delle aree protette. A Cipro, la rimozione dell'acacia verrà ripetuta attraverso fondi governativi. Infine, i vivai regionali saranno impegnati nella propagazione delle specie vegetali native delle aree costiere, contribuendo così alla preservazione del patrimonio genetico locale. Queste sinergie tra istituzioni e stakeholder saranno fondamentali per garantire il successo e la sostenibilità a lungo termine del progetto LIFE CALLIOPE. Le attività di divulgazione e disseminazione verranno continuate negli anni successivi.

Looking ahead to the future of the project, there is a planned ongoing involvement of universities in monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness of conservation actions. Additionally, local authorities responsible for maintaining the implemented works will play a crucial role in ensuring the continuity and success of protection initiatives and sustainable management of coastal and marine environments. Stakeholders will be called upon to actively contribute their support and resources to ensure the maintenance and development of protected areas. In Cyprus, the removal of acacia will be repeated using government funds. Finally, regional nurseries will be engaged in propagating native plant species of coastal areas, thus contributing to the preservation of local genetic heritage. These synergies between institutions and stakeholders will be essential to ensure the long-term success and sustainability of the LIFE CALLIOPE project. Outreach and dissemination activities will continue in the years to come.

LIFE CALLIOPE

LIFE17 NAT/IT/000565 "CALLIOPE"
COASTAL DUNE HABITATS,
SUBLITTORAL SANDBANK, MARINE REEFS:
CONSERVATION, PROTECTION, AND THREATS MITIGATION

UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI
DEL MOLISE

Beneficiario coordinatore: Regione Abruzzo (Italia) **Beneficiari associati:** Ministero dell'Agricoltura, Sviluppo Rurale e Ambiente (Cipro), Università degli Studi del Molise (Italia), Università Frederick (Cipro), C.I.R.S.P.E. - Centro Italiano Ricerche e Studi per la Pesca (Italia) **Durata:** 09/2018 - 09/2024 **Budget complessivo:** 1.928.505 Euro **Contributo EU:** 1.157.103 Euro

Coordinator Beneficiary: Abruzzo Region (Italy)

Associated Beneficiaries: Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development and Environment (Cyprus), University of Molise (Italy), Frederick University (Cyprus), C.I.R.S.P.E. - Italian Center for Research and Studies on Fishing (Italy)

Duration : 09/2018 - 09/2024

Total Budget: 1,928,505 Euros

EU Contribution: 1,157,103 Euros

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LIFE CALLIOPE

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DEGLI STUDI
DEL MOLISE

Οι βέλτιστες πρακτικές του έργου LIFE CALLIOPE The best practices of the LIFE CALLIOPE Project Layman's Report

ITALY, ABRUZZO REGION

SAC IT7120215 Torre del Cerrano

pSCI Ripari di Giobbe – Foce del Fiume Foro

pSCI Punta dell'Acquabella – Foce del Fiume Moro

SAC IT7140107 Lecceta di Torino di Sangro - Foce del Fiume Sangro

SAC IT7140108 Punta Aderci – Punta della Penna

SAC IT7140109 Marina di Vasto

CYPRUS

SAC CY4000001 Periochi Polis - Gialia

- Το έργο LIFE CALLIOPE (Οικότοποι παράκτιων αμμόλοφων, υποπαραθαλάσσιες αμμόδεις όχθες, θαλάσσιοι ύφαλοι: διατήρηση, προστασία και μετριασμός απειλών- LIFE 17 NAT/IT/000565) είναι ένα έργο που χρηματοδοτήθηκε από την Ευρωπαϊκή Επιτροπή για την προστασία των ευαίσθητων παράκτιων και θαλάσσιων οικοσυστημάτων και τον μετριασμό των επιπτώσεων από τις ανθρώπινες δραστηριότητες κατά μήκος της ακτής της περιοχής Αμπρούτσο στην Ιταλία και των βορειοδυτικών ακτών της Κύπρου.
- Αυτές οι περιοχές συχνά αλλοιώνονται από ανθρώπινες δραστηριότητες που βλάπτουν τη βιοποικιλότητα στις αμμοθίνες και στους αμμόδεις και βραχώδεις βυθούς. Μεταξύ των αλλαγών που προκαλούνται από τον άνθρωπο είναι η ισοπέδωση και τσιμεντοποίηση των αμμοθινών, η υποβάθμιση των φυσικών οικοσυστημάτων, η υπερβολική αλιεία και η χρήση καταστροφικών πρακτικών σε βυθούς και βραχώδεις ακτές.
- Για την προστασία αυτών των πολύτιμων οικοσυστημάτων, είναι απαραίτητο να υιοθετηθούν καλές πρακτικές που να επιτρέπουν τη διατήρηση της φυσικής κληρονομιάς και της ομορφιάς των παράκτιων οικοσυστημάτων.

Περιοχές του δικτύου Natura 2000, όπου υλοποιείται το έργο: SAC IT7120215 Torre del Cerrano, pSCI Ripari di Giobbe - Foce del Fiume Foro, pSCI Punta dell'Acquabella - Foce del Fiume Moro, SAC IT7140107 Lecceta litoranea di Torino di Sangro e Foce del Fiume Sangro, SAC IT7140108 Punta Aderci - Punta della Penna, SAC IT7140109 Marina di Vasto (Ιταλία), SAC CY4000001 Περιοχή Πόλης - Γιαλιά (Κύπρος)

- LIFE CALLIOPE (Coastal dune habitats, sublittoral sandbanks, marine reefs: Conservation, Protection, and Threats Mitigation - LIFE 17 NAT/IT/000565) is a project funded by the European Community to protect fragile coastal dune and marine ecosystems and mitigate the impacts of human activities along the Abruzzo coastline in Italy, and the northwestern coasts of Cyprus.

- These areas are often altered by human activities that damage the biodiversity of dunes, sandy and rocky seabeds. Among the changes induced by humans are the leveling and cementing of dune areas, degradation of natural environments, excessive fishing and the use of destructive methods in seabeds and cliffs.

- To safeguard these precious environments, it is necessary to adopt good practices that allow for the preservation of natural heritage and the beauty of coastal landscapes.

Localization: Sites of the Natura 2000 network. SAC IT7120215 Torre del Cerrano, pSCI Ripari di Giobbe – Foce del Fiume Foro, pSCI Punta dell’Acquabella – Foce del Fiume Moro, SAC IT7140107 Lecceta litoranea di Torino di Sangro e Foce del Fiume Sangro, SAC IT7140108 Punta Aderci - Punta della Penna, SAC IT7140109 Marina di Vasto (Italy), SAC CY4000001 Periochi Polis - Gialia (Cyprus).

Οι στόχοι του έργου ήταν:

1. Αποκατάσταση κι ενίσχυση των οικοτόπων κοινοτικού ενδιαφέροντος εντός των περιοχών-στόχων του έργου που περιλαμβάνονται στο δίκτυο Natura 2000.
2. Δημιουργία νέων παράκτιων περιοχών εντός του δικτύου Natura 2000 κι επέκταση υφιστάμενων περιοχών.
3. Μελέτη των κοινωνικο-οικονομικών επιπτώσεων του έργου.
4. Ευαισθητοποίηση του κοινού σε περιβαλλοντικά θέματα.

The objectives of the project were:

1. Recovery and enhancement of the habitats of community interest within the Natura 2000 sites involved in the project.
2. Establishment of new coastal sites within the Natura 2000 network and the extension of existing sites into marine areas.
3. Study of the socio-economic impact of the project.
4. Public awareness raising on environmental issues.

Οικοσύστημα παράκτιων αμμοθινών

Οι αμμόδεις παράκτιες αμμοθίνες είναι πολύ μοναδικό οικοσύστημα από οικολογική, βιολογική και χωρική άποψη. Οι δύσκολες αβιοτικές συνθήκες περιβάλλοντος (άνεμος, αλάτι, ασταθές υπόστρωμα) οδηγούν στην παρουσία εξαιρετικά εξειδικευμένων φυτών και ζώων. Οι αμμόδεις αμμοθίνες παρέχουν σημαντικές οικοσυστημικές υπηρεσίες, όπως η διατήρηση ενδιαιτημάτων για απειλούμενη βιοποικιλότητα, η προστασία των γειτονικών περιοχών από τις επιπτώσεις του ανέμου και του αλατιού, η αντιμετώπιση της παράκτιας διάβρωσης και η προσφορά υπηρεσιών τουριστικού ενδιαφέροντος σχετικών με το κολύμπι και άλλες δραστηριότητες αναψυχής.

Coastal Dune Environments

Sandy coastal dunes are very unique ecosystems from an ecological, biological, and landscape perspective. The challenging living conditions (wind, salt, unstable substrate) result in the presence of highly specialized plants and animals. Sandy dunes provide important ecosystem services, such as maintaining habitats for threatened biodiversity, protecting the interdunal areas from the effects of wind and salt, countering coastal erosion, and offering tourist appeal related to swimming and other recreational activities.

Αμμόδεις θαλάσσιοι βυθοί

Βυθοί με αραιή βλάστηση που εκπροσωπούνται από κάποια φύκη και το θαλάσσιο φυτό *Cymodocea nodosa*. Φιλοξενούν είδη όπως ο ιππόκαμπος (*Hippocampus hippocampus*), δίθυρα όπως η *Chamelea gallina* και το *Lentidium mediterraneum*, γαστερόποδα όπως το *Aporrhais pespelecani*, και εχινόδερμα όπως ο αστερίας.

The Sandy Submerged Environments

Seabeds with sparse vegetation represented by some algae and the underwater plant *Cymodocea nodosa*. They host species such as the seahorse (*Hippocampus hippocampus*), bivalves like *Chamelea gallina* and *Lentidium mediterraneum*, gastropods like *Aporrhais pespelecani*, and echinoderms like starfish.

Οικοσύστημα Υφάλων

Η παράκτια ζώνη της περιοχής Αμπρούτσο (Ιταλία) χαρακτηρίζεται στο νότιο τμήμα από βράχια που βυθίζονται στη θάλασσα, δημιουργώντας θαλάσσιους υφάλους πλούσιους σε βιοποικιλότητα. Ορισμένοι βράχοι σχηματίζονται από κρούστες και εγκλείσεις κοραλλιών, σκουληκιών και δίθυρων, τόσο ζωντανών όσο και νεκρών. Υπάρχουν επίσης πολλά φύκη σε συνδυασμό με την παρουσία γυμνοβράγχιων, καρκινοειδών και ψαριών.

The Reef Environments

The coastal territory of the Abruzzo coast is characterized in the southern part by cliffs that plunge into the sea, creating submerged reefs rich in biodiversity. Some rocks are formed by concretions and encrustations of corals, worms, and bivalves, both living and dead. There are also many algae, with the presence of nudibranchs, crustaceans, and fish.

Habitat e specie target

Habitat and target species

Vegetazione rada della spiaggia
1210: Vegetazione annua delle linee
di deposito marine: formazioni erbacee, annuali

Sparse vegetation of the beach
1210: Annual vegetation of marine deposit lines:
herbaceous, annual formations

Vegetazione del piede delle dune
2110: Dune embrionali mobili

Vegetation of the dune foot
2110: Shifting embryonic dunes

Vegetazione delle dune - 2120: Dune mobili del cordone
litorale con presenza di *Ammophila arenaria* (dune bianche)

Vegetation of the dunes - 2120: Shifting coastal dunes
with the presence of *Ammophila arenaria* (white dunes)

Vegetazione delle radure dunali
2230: Dune con prati de *Malcolmietalia*

Vegetation of the dune clearings
2230: Dunes with grasslands of *Malcolmietalia*

Macchia mediterranea con ginepri
2250*: Dune costiere con *Juniperus* spp.

Mediterranean scrub with junipers
2250*: Coastal dunes with *Juniperus* spp.

Vegetazione degli ambienti umidi retrodunali
1410: Pascoli inondati mediterranei
(*Juncetalia maritimi*)

Vegetation of humid interdunal environments
1410: Mediterranean salt meadows
(*Juncetalia maritimi*)

Χελώνα του Χέρμαν (μεσογειακή χελώνα) - Hermann's Tortoise (*Testudo hermanni* Gmelin, 1789)

Ανάμεσα στα τρία είδη χερσαίων χελωνών που υπάρχουν στην Ιταλία, η *Testudo hermanni* θεωρείται το πιο απειλούμενο είδος, σε εθνικό επίπεδο. Η κατανομή του είδους στην ιταλική χερσόνησο έχει υποστεί μια αργή και συνεχή συρρίκνωση λόγω της προοδευτικής μείωσης, κατακερματισμού και υποβάθμισης των φυσικών και ημιφυσικών ενδιαιτημάτων που είναι κατάλληλα για τη διατήρησή της. Σήμερα, χαρακτηρίζεται είδος "Εύτρωτο" στον Κόκκινο Κατάλογο των Ιταλικών Σπονδυλωτών της IUCN. Για τον λόγο αυτό εμπίπτει σε διάφορα καθεστώτα προστασίας.

Among the three species of terrestrial tortoises present in Italy *Testudo hermanni* is considered the most at risk at the national level. The distribution of the species in the Italian peninsula has undergone a slow and continuous contraction due to the progressive reduction, fragmentation, and degradation of natural and semi-natural habitats suitable for its conservation. Today, it is considered a species "vulnerable" in the IUCN Red List of Italian Vertebrates; it is therefore subject to various protection regimes.

Λιθοφάγα (πετροσωλήνας)- Date Mussel *Lithophaga lithophaga* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Το συγκεκριμένο δίθυρο έχει ρυθμό ανάπτυξης λίγων χιλιοστών ανά έτος. Αποικίζει πλήρως τις ανεπαρκώς φωτισμένες κοιλότητες των βράχων, ακόμα και σε ρηχά βάθη. Η παρουσία του τροποποιεί τον βράχο και επιτρέπει την αποίκιση από πολλά άλλα θαλάσσια είδη πανίδας που αλλιώς δεν θα μπορούσαν να εγκατασταθούν στον γυμνό βράχο. Η αλίευση και κατανάλωσή του είναι παράνομη, επειδή η εξαγωγή των ατόμων απαιτεί την πλήρη θραύση του βράχου που τα φιλοξενεί, προκαλώντας σοβαρές ζημιές στο οικοσύστημα.

The Date Mussel has a growth rate of a few millimeters per year. It entirely colonizes the poorly lit cavities of cliffs, even at shallow depths. Its presence modifies the rock and allows the colonization of many other marine species that would otherwise be unable to establish themselves on bare rock. The fishing and consumption of the date mussel are illegal because extracting the individuals requires completely breaking the rock that hosts them, causing severe damage to the cliff habitat.

Maresia nana var. glabra (Meikle) Christodoulou & Hand

Η *Maresia nana var. glabra* είναι μια ενδημική ποικιλία της Κύπρου, που βρίσκεται μόνο στην συγκεκριμένη περιοχή - στόχο και πουθενά αλλού στον κόσμο. Είναι ετήσια πόα, με μικρά, μωβ άνθη. Έχει λεία φύλλα και βλαστούς, σε αντίθεση με την πιο διαδεδομένη ποικιλία του είδους που έχει αστεροειδείς τρίχες. Η κατάσταση διατήρησής της αξιολογείται ως «Κρισίμως Κινδυνεύον» σύμφωνα με τα κριτήρια της IUCN και περιλαμβάνεται στο Κόκκινο Βιβλίο της Χλωρίδας της Κύπρου.

Maresia nana var. glabra is a Cyprus endemic variety, found only at the target site and nowhere else in the world. It is annual, with small, mauve flowers. It has smooth leaves and stems, in contrast to the more widespread species that have stellate hairs. Its conservation status is evaluated as Critically Endangered based on the criteria of IUCN, and included in the Red Data Book of the Flora of Cyprus.

Προκαταρκτικές δράσεις και η σημασία τους στην υλοποίηση του έργου

Preliminary studies and their value for project implementation

Χάρη στις προκαταρκτικές δράσεις του έργου από ερευνητές των δύο πανεπιστημίων που συμμετέχουν, ήταν δυνατόν να οριστούν και να χαρτογραφηθούν με ακρίβεια η κατανομή των οικοτόπων και των ειδών που χρειάζονται διατήρηση και να εκτιμηθεί λεπτομερώς η κατάσταση διατήρησής τους. Αυτά τα δεδομένα χρησίμευσαν, κατά την υλοποίηση του έργου, ως βάση για την αξιολόγηση της αποτελεσματικότητας των δράσεων διατήρησης, εκτιμώντας τα οφέλη για τους οικοτόπους και είδη στόχους. Αυτές οι πληροφορίες ήταν κρίσιμες για την καθοδήγηση των μέτρων διατήρησης και διαχείρισης των παράκτιων και θαλάσσιων οικοτόπων στις περιοχές όπου υλοποιείται το έργο LIFE CALLIOPE.

Thanks to the studies and investigations conducted during the preliminary phase of the project by researchers from the two universities involved, it was possible to accurately define and map the distribution of habitats and species of conservation value and assess their conservation status in detail. These data then served as a basis for evaluating, during the project implementation, the effectiveness of the actions taken, measuring the benefits to the target habitats and species. This information will be crucial for guiding conservation and management measures for coastal and marine environments in the areas involved in the LIFE CALLIOPE project.

Επεμβάσεις αποκατάστασης και προστασίας / Η προστασία των αμμοθινικών οικοτόπων

Environmental Restoration and Protection Interventions

The protection of dune habitats

Το ποδοπάτημα και η καταστροφή του εδάφους αποτελούν σοβαρές απειλές για τη διατήρηση των αμμοθινών καθώς προκαλούν υποβάθμιση των οικοτόπων και μείωση της βιοποικιλότητας. Για την αντιμετώπιση αυτού του ζητήματος, το έργο προχώρησε στην κατασκευή διάφορων δομών για την προστασία περίπου 22 εκταρίων αμμοθινικών οικοτόπων:

- α) 240 γραμμικά μέτρα πεζοδρόμων που διασχίζουν τις αμμοθίνες από την ενδοχώρα προς την παραλία
- β) 2344 μέτρα πασσάλων ενωμένων με σχοινί για την περίφραξη των αμμοθινών και την αποτροπή του ποδοπατήματος
- γ) 1 μπάρα για να αποτρέψει την είσοδο μηχανοκίνητων οχημάτων στις αμμοθίνες
- δ) 60 γραμμικά μέτρα συρματόδετων κιβωτίων (gabions) για να αποτρέψουν την πρόσβαση οχημάτων στην παραλία. Επιπλέον, εγκαταστάθηκαν 17 πίνακες για την ενημέρωση των λουόμενων για το περιβάλλον.

Trampling and land consumption represent a serious threat to the conservation of dunes as they cause habitat degradation and a decline in biodiversity. To address this issue, the project includes the construction of various structures to protect approximately 22 hectares of dune habitats:

- a) 240 linear meters of pedestrian walkways that cross the dunes from the inland to the beach;
- b) 2344 meters of posts and rope to delimit the dunes and prevent trampling;
- c) 1 access barrier to prevent motor vehicles from entering the dunes;
- d) 60 linear meters of gabions to deter vehicle access to the beach. Additionally, 17 panels have been installed to inform beachgoers about the environmental.

Επεμβάσεις αποκατάστασης και προστασίας / Ο πολλαπλασιασμός ιθαγενών ειδών

Environmental Restoration and Protection Interventions The propagation of native species

Η αποκατάσταση της βλάστησης των αμμοθινών μέσω της φύτευσης ιθαγενών ειδών είναι κρίσιμη για την επαναφορά των υποβαθμισμένων αμμοθινών παράκτιων οικοσυστημάτων στην αρχική τους κατάσταση. Ερευνητές από το Πανεπιστήμιο του Molise συγκέντρωσαν σπέρματα (σπόρους) και μοσχεύματα ιθαγενών ειδών των αμμοθινών και τα καλλιέργησαν με την υποστήριξη του Περιφερειακού Δασικού Φυτωρίου “Le Marinelle” στη Marina di Petacciato (Ιταλία). Το Πανεπιστήμιο του Molise, σε συνεργασία με το Δασικό Φυτώριο, ανέπτυξε επίσης ένα αποτελεσματικό «Πρωτόκολλο φύτευσης για ιθαγενή είδη των αμμοθινών», το οποίο είναι διαθέσιμο στο Εγχειρίδιο Αναπαραγωγής Ειδών σε Αδριατικά Περιβάλλοντα Αμμοθινών. Ερευνητές από το Πανεπιστήμιο Frederick στην Κύπρο συγκέντρωσαν 4.000 σπόρους του ενδημικού φυτού *Maresia nana var. glabra* και υλοποίησαν πειράματα φύτευσης. Από τα πειράματα προέκυψε το «Πρωτόκολλο φύτευσης για το ενδημικό φυτό *Maresia nana var. glabra*». Τα αρτίβλαστα που προέκυψαν από τα πειράματα φύτευσης, φυτεύτηκαν στην περιοχή μελέτης για την ενίσχυση του πληθυσμού του είδους.

The restoration of dune vegetation through the planting of native species is crucial for returning degraded sandy coastal environments to their original ecosystems. Researchers from the University of Molise collected seeds and cuttings of native dune species and cultivated them with the support of the Regional Forest Nursery “Le Marinelle” in Marina di Petacciato, Italy, and the Nursery of Frederick University in Cyprus. The University of Molise, in collaboration with the Forest Nursery, also developed an effective protocol for obtaining germination from seeds of native dune species, which is made available in the Manual for the Propagation of Species in Adriatic Dune Environments.

Researchers from Frederick University in Cyprus collected 4,000 seeds of the endemic species *Maresia nana var. glabra* and propagated this species, making it available for planting on Cypriot

dunes.

Επεμβάσεις αποκατάστασης και προστασίας / Η αποκατάσταση των αμμοθινών

Environmental Restoration and Protection Interventions The biorestore of dunes

Η βλάστηση των αμμοθινών παίζει κρίσιμο ρόλο στη σταθεροποίηση του αμμώδους υποστρώματος. Η απώλειά της θέτει σε κίνδυνο ολόκληρο το οικοσύστημα των αμμοθινών, επιταχύνοντας την παράκτια διάβρωση και προκαλώντας σημαντική ζημιά στο φυσικό περιβάλλον, συμπεριλαμβανομένης της απώλειας των παραλιών. Η αποκατάσταση της συνέχειας των κινούμενων αμμοθινών επιτεύχθηκε σε συνολική έκταση 33 εκταρίων, με τη φύτευση πάνω από 10.433 δενδρυλλίων ιθαγενών ειδών των αμμοθινών, που φύτεψαν από σπέρματα (σπόρους) που συλλέχθηκαν συγκεκριμένες περιοχές. Αυτή η προσέγγιση έχει επιτρέψει την αποκατάσταση περίπου 17 εκταρίων οικοτόπων κατάλληλων για την επιβίωση και αναπαραγωγή του είδους στόχου *Testudo hermanni*.

Dune vegetation plays a crucial role in stabilizing sandy sediment. Its loss compromises the entire dune zonation, accelerating coastal erosion and causing significant damage to the natural environment, including the loss of beaches. The reconstruction of the continuity of mobile dune systems was achieved over a total of 33 hectares, involving the planting of over 10,433 seedlings of native dune species, produced from locally sourced seeds collected in geographically and ecologically consistent sites. This approach has allowed for the rehabilitation of approximately 17 hectares of suitable habitat for the survival and reproduction of the target species *Testudo hermanni*.

Επεμβάσεις αποκατάστασης και προστασίας / Η καταπολέμηση ξενικών εισβλητικών ειδών

Environmental Restoration and Protection Interventions The eradication of alien species

Τα ξενικά εισβλητικά είδη αποτελούν σοβαρή απειλή για τη παγκόσμια βιοποικιλότητα. Στην παράκτια ζώνη της «Περιοχής Πόλης - Γιαλιά» στην Κύπρο, έχουν βρεθεί φυτά *Acacia saligna*, ένα ξενικό εισβλητικό είδος που χαρακτηρίζεται από την υψηλή αναπαραγωγική του ικανότητα και την ταχεία εξάπλωσή του σε μεσογειακά αμμοθινικά περιβάλλοντα. Η απομάκρυνση των περισσότερων φυτών ακακίας έχει οδηγήσει στην αποκατάσταση περίπου 12,4 εκταρίων αμμοθινικών οικοτόπων. Επιπλέον, στην ίδια τοποθεσία, απομακρύνθηκαν απόβλητα από παλαιότερες δραστηριότητες εξόρυξης από μια περιοχή 1,7 εκταρίων.

Invasive alien species pose a serious threat to global biodiversity. At the coastal site 'Periochi Polis - Gialia' in Cyprus, plants of *Acacia saligna*, an exotic invasive species characterized by its high reproductive capacity and rapid spread in Mediterranean dune environments, have been found. The removal of most of the acacia plants has led to the rehabilitation of approximately 12.4 hectares of habitat 2250* (coastal dunes with *Juniperus* spp.). Additionally, in the same location, quarry waste was removed from an area of 1.7 hectares.

Επεμβάσεις αποκατάστασης και προστασίας / Η δημιουργία ενός πάρκου σημαδούρων για την προστασία του θαλάσσιου περιβάλλοντος

Environmental Restoration and Protection Interventions The creation of the buoy park for the protection of marine environments

Στην περιοχή Abruzzo, η βιοποικιλότητα των θαλάσσιων βράχων και των βενθικών λιβαδιών προστατεύθηκε σε μια έκταση 347,12 εκταρίων εντός των περιοχών Natura 2000 pSCI Ripari di Giobbe - Foce del Fiume Foro, pSCI Punta dell'Acquabella - Foce del Fiume Moro, και SAC IT7140108 Punta Aderci - Punta della Penna, με τη ρύθμιση της πρόσβασης και την οριοθέτηση της περιοχής με 12 σημαδούρες. Επιπλέον, αυτή η ενέργεια επέτρεψε την αποκατάσταση περίπου 24,91 εκταρίων οικοτόπου κατάλληλου για την επιβίωση και αναπαραγωγή του είδους στόχου *Lithophaga lithophaga*.

In Abruzzo, the biodiversity of marine cliffs and submerged meadows has been protected over an area of 347.12 hectares within the Natura 2000 sites pSCI Ripari di Giobbe - Foce del Fiume Foro, pSCI Punta dell'Acquabella - Foce del Fiume Moro, and SAC IT7140108 Punta Aderci - Punta della Penna, by regulating access and delineating the area with 12 marker buoys. Additionally, this action has enabled the recovery of approximately 24.91 hectares of suitable habitat for the survival and reproduction of the target species *Lithophaga lithophaga*.

Σχέδιο Δράσης για την προστασία της ακτής Abruzzo

Action Plan for the Protection of the Abruzzo Coast

Το έργο περιέλαβε τη δημιουργία ενός Περιφερειακού Σχεδίου Δράσης για τη βιώσιμη διαχείριση των εναπομεινάντων φυσικών οικοσυστημάτων κατά μήκος ολόκληρης της ακτής Abruzzo (Ιταλία). Η υιοθέτηση καλών πρακτικών διαχείρισης για τις αμμοθίνες θα επιτρέψει την επέκταση του διαθέσιμου οικοτόπου για τα εμβληματικά είδη όπως ο Αλκυώνιος (*Charadrius alexandrinus*) και η χελώνα (*Testudo hermanni*). Το Περιφερειακό Σχέδιο Δράσης περιέχει περιγραφή και χαρτογράφηση της βλάστησης των αμμοθινών στις Ειδικές Περιοχές Διατήρησης του Δικτύου Natura 2000, στα Περιφερειακά Παράκτια Φυσικά Αποθέματα και σε δημόσιες περιοχές με αμμοθινικούς οικότοπους που έχουν αξία διατήρησης. Το Σχέδιο Δράσης κοινοποιήθηκε στους παράκτιους δήμους και στα διαχειριστικά όργανα προστατευόμενων περιοχών κατά τις συναντήσεις που πραγματοποιήθηκαν σε Pescara και Ortona (Ιταλία).

The project included the creation of a Regional Coastal Action Plan for the sustainable management of the remaining natural environments along the entire Abruzzo coast. The adoption of good management practices for dune areas will allow the enlargement of dune habitat available for the flagship species such as the Kentish plover (*Charadrius alexandrinus*) and the Hermann's tortoise (*Testudo hermanni*). The Regional Coastal Action Plan of the Abruzzo Region (ARCA) included the description and mapping of dune vegetation in the Special Areas of Conservation of the Natura 2000 Network, in the Regional Coastal Nature Reserves, and in public areas with dune habitats of conservation value. The ARCA Plan was shared with coastal municipalities and the managing bodies of protected areas during meetings held in Pescara and Ortona (CH), Italy.

Εφαρμογή του δικτύου Natura 2000

Implementation of the Natura 2000 Network

Μία από τις σημαντικότερες ενέργειες του έργου ήταν η επέκταση του δικτύου Natura 2000 με την ίδρυση δύο νέων παράκτιων-θαλάσσιων Τόπων Κοινοτικού Ενδιαφέροντος (pSCI) στην Ortona: Ripari di Giobbe - Foce del Fiume Foro και Punta dell'Acquabella - Foce del Fiume Moro, συνολικής έκτασης περίπου 275 εκταρίων. Επιπλέον, η θαλάσσια έκταση της Ειδικής Ζώνης Διατήρησης (SAC) IT7140108 Punta Aderci - Punta della Penna επεκτάθηκε κατά περίπου 216 εκτάρια. Το έργο LIFE CALLIOPE επέτρεψε έτσι την προστασία των θαλάσσιων βραχωδών υφάλων και των αμμωδών βυθών συνολικής έκτασης περίπου 347 εκταρίων. Οι θαλάσσιες περιοχές περιλαμβάνουν αυτές που εκτείνονται περίπου 300 μέτρα προς τη θάλασσα, καλύπτοντας τα πρώτα 10 μέτρα βάρους

One of the most significant actions of the project was the expansion of the Natura 2000 network with the establishment of two new coastal-sea Sites of Community Importance (pSCI) in Ortona: Ripari di Giobbe – Foce del Fiume Foro and Punta dell'Acquabella – Foce del Fiume Moro, totaling approximately 275 hectares. Additionally, the marine extension of the Site of Community Importance (SAC) IT7140108 Punta Aderci – Punta della Penna was expanded by approximately 216 hectares. The LIFE CALLIOPE project thus enabled the protection of submerged rocky reef and sandy seabed environments totaling approximately 347 hectares. The marine areas include those adjacent to the coast for about 300 meters seaward, encompassing the first 10 meters of depth.

Η οικολογική παρακολούθηση

The ecological monitoring

Οι δραστηριότητες παρακολούθησης των οικοτόπων και ειδών στόχων πραγματοποιούνταν συνεχώς κατά τη διάρκεια των πέντε ετών του έργου από ερευνητές των εμπλεκόμενων πανεπιστημίων, στις θέσεις όπου υλοποιήθηκαν επεμβάσεις αποκατάστασης και προστασίας του οικοσυστήματος. Για το αμμοθινικό οικοσύστημα, αναγνωρίστηκαν 68 θέσεις παρακολούθησης της βλάστησης στην Ιταλία και 8 θέσεις στην Κύπρο. Η κάλυψη των χλωριδικών ειδών που παρουσιάζονται καταγράφηκε για κάθε θέση παρακολούθησης. Η παρακολούθηση έγινε πριν, κατά τη διάρκεια και μετά την εφαρμογή των δράσεων διατήρησης (Δράσεις C), αξιολογώντας την επίδραση στους οικοτόπους στόχους, χρησιμοποιώντας την παρουσία και την αφθονία των ειδών.

Όσον αφορά τα ζωικά είδη, πραγματοποιήθηκαν 11 γραμμικές διατομές μήκους περίπου 1 χλμ, κάθετα προς την ακτογραμμή, για την παρακολούθηση ερπετών, και 17 γραμμικές διατομές μήκους περίπου 300 μ, παράλληλα προς την ακτογραμμή, για την παρακολούθηση πουλιών. Για τα θαλάσσια περιβάλλοντα, πραγματοποιήθηκαν υποβρύχιες έρευνες σε 10 θέσεις.

Τα δεδομένα που αποκτήθηκαν χρησιμοποιήθηκαν για την ενημέρωση των τυποποιημένων εντύπων και των χαρτών των οικοτόπων των περιοχών του Δικτύου Natura 2000 όπου υλοποιήθηκε το έργο. Επιπλέον, αυτές οι περιοχές θα παρακολουθούνται με την πάροδο του χρόνου από ερευνητές των δύο πανεπιστημίων για να ενημερώνονται περιοδικά οι πληροφορίες βιοποικιλότητας στις περιοχές στόχους του έργου, ακόμα και μετά την ολοκλήρωση του έργου.

The monitoring activities of habitats and species were carried out continuously over the five years of the project by researchers from the involved universities in the areas affected by the restoration and environmental protection interventions. For dune environments, 68 vegetation monitoring areas were identified in Italy and 8 areas in Cyprus at the sites where renaturalization interventions were carried out. The coverage of vascular plant species present was recorded for each monitoring area. Monitoring took place before, during, and after the implementation of conservation actions (Actions C), evaluating the impact on the target habitats by using species richness and abundance.

Regarding faunal species, 11 linear transects approximately 1 km long, transverse to the coastline, were conducted for reptile observation, and 17 linear transects approximately 300 m long, parallel to the coastline, were conducted for bird monitoring. For marine environments, scuba diving surveys were conducted, and 10 areas were monitored.

The acquired data were used to update the standard forms and habitat maps of the community interest sites of the Natura 2000 Network involved in the project. Additionally, these sites will be monitored over time by researchers from the two universities to periodically update biodiversity information in the project's target areas, even after the project's conclusion.

Κοινωνικο-οικονομική επίδραση του έργου

Socio-economic Impact of the Project

Σκοπός της δράσης ήταν η αξιολόγηση των κοινωνικών και οικονομικών επιπτώσεων των επεμβάσεων που πραγματοποιήθηκαν από το Έργο LIFE CALLIOPE. Για τον σκοπό αυτό, εντοπίστηκαν πιθανές επιπτώσεις τόσο στην οικονομική διάσταση (μικροοικονομική και μακροοικονομική), όσο και στη χωρική κλίμακα (τοπική και παγκόσμια). Για την εξέταση της οικονομικής διάστασης, επιλέχθηκαν δείκτες για την αξιολόγηση των επιπτώσεων τόσο σε ατομικό επίπεδο και ενδιαφερόμενων φορέων που λειτουργούν στην περιοχή (μικροοικονομική) όσο και στην κοινότητα και τους πολίτες γενικότερα (μακροοικονομική). Όσον αφορά τη χωρική κλίμακα, εξετάστηκαν οι πιθανές επιπτώσεις σε μεμονωμένες τοποθεσίες (τοπική), καθώς και σε ευρύτερη κλίμακα όπως η περιφερειακή και η εθνική κλίμακα (παγκόσμια). Στην ανάλυση, ενεργό ρόλο έπαιξαν δημόσιοι και ιδιωτικοί ενδιαφερόμενοι φορείς και η τοπική κοινότητα, που συμμετείχαν σε έρευνα για την αξιολόγηση της βελτίωσης της κοινωνικής και περιβαλλοντικής ευημερίας που προήλθε από τις επεμβάσεις του έργου. Για τον σκοπό αυτό, έγινε επιλογή και επικοινωνία με περισσότερα από 250 άτομα από τον τομέα του τουρισμού και 30 δημόσιοι (π.χ. τοπικές αρχές) και ιδιωτικοί ενδιαφερόμενοι φορείς (π.χ. πολίτες)

The objective of the Action was to assess the social and economic impacts of the interventions carried out by the LIFE CALLIOPE Project. To this end, potential impacts on both the economic dimension (micro and macro) and the territorial scale (local and global) were identified. To investigate the economic dimension, indicators were selected to assess externalities on both entities and stakeholders operating in the territory (micro) and on the community and citizens in general (macro). Regarding the territorial scale, possible impacts on individual sites (local) were considered, as well as on a broader scale such as the regional and national levels (global). In the analysis, an active role was played by public and private stakeholders and the local community involved in a survey to evaluate the improvement of social and environmental well being generated by project interventions. To this end, more than 250 operators in the tourism sector and 30 public (e.g., local authorities) and private stakeholders (e.g., citizens) were selected and contacted.

Αξιολόγηση οικοσυστημικών υπηρεσιών

Assessment of Ecosystem Services

Στη δράση αυτή, έγινε αξιολόγηση των περιβαλλοντικών και οικονομικών πλεονεκτημάτων που προσφέρουν οι περιοχές του δικτύου Natura 2000 και η βάση χρηστών που αντιπροσωπεύεται από τους τελικούς καταναλωτές. Για τον σκοπό αυτό, προσδιορίστηκαν και εφαρμόστηκαν μεθοδολογίες για την ποσοτικοποίηση της βιοφυσικής και οικονομικής αξιολόγησης τεσσάρων οικοσυστημικών υπηρεσιών: Ενδιαίτημα Βιοποικιλότητας, Προστασία από Διάβρωση, Δέσμευση Διοξειδίου του Άνθρακα και Αξία Αναψυχής. Η συνολική εκτιμώμενη αξία για αυτές τις οικοσυστημικές υπηρεσίες υπερβαίνει τα 8 εκατομμύρια ευρώ, με μέσο όρο περίπου 1.400 ευρώ ανά εκτάριο. Εκτός από τον μόνιμο πληθυσμό, οι κύριοι ωφελοούμενοι είναι οι τουρίστες. Επιπλέον, οι ενέργειες διατήρησης που ελήφθησαν προστατεύουν τις υποδομές που εκτίθενται στον κίνδυνο παράκτιας διάβρωσης, όπως θέρετρα παραλίας, λιμάνια και εμπορικές δραστηριότητες.

Within this action, the environmental and economic benefits offered by the Natura 2000 Sites and the user base represented by end-consumers were evaluated. To this end, methodologies for the quantification of biophysical and economic assessment of four ecosystem services were identified and implemented: Biodiversity Habitat, Erosion Protection, Carbon Sequestration, and Recreational Value. The overall estimated value for these ecosystem services exceeds 8 million euros, with an average of approximately 1,400 euros per hectare. In addition to the resident population, the main beneficiaries are tourists. Furthermore, the conservation actions taken protect the infrastructure exposed to the risk of coastal erosion, such as beach resorts, ports, and commercial activities.

Διάχυση και Ευαισθητοποίηση

Communication and Awareness

Οι δράσεις διατήρησης συνοδεύτηκαν από πολλές δραστηριότητες διάχυσης, ευαισθητοποίησης και εμπλοκής που απευθύνονταν σε μαθητές, κατοίκους, τουρίστες και τοπικούς φορείς, με σκοπό την αύξηση της ευαισθητοποίησης για τη φυσική κληρονομιά και τα περιβαλλοντικά θέματα των ακτών του Abruzzo και της Κύπρου. Δημιουργήθηκαν ενημερωτικά φυλλάδια, ενημερωτικές πινακίδες τοποθετημένες στις περιοχές στόχους, οπτικοακουστικό υλικό (4 βίντεο και 2 ντοκιμαντέρ), θεματικά roll-up και ενημερωτικό δελτίο για τις δραστηριότητες του έργου. Εκδόθηκαν επίσης δελτία τύπου και έγιναν συνεντεύξεις που δημοσιεύθηκαν από τα τοπικά μέσα ενημέρωσης. Έγιναν μαθήματα στην τάξη και ξεναγήσεις με εμπλοκή 21 σχολείων και τη συμμετοχή περίπου 1.500 παιδιών, σύμφωνα με τους περιορισμούς λόγω της πανδημίας Covid-19. Η ιστοσελίδα του έργου (διαθέσιμη στα ιταλικά και στα αγγλικά), καθώς και η σελίδα του έργου στο Facebook χρησίμευσαν ως εργαλεία για τη διάδοση πληροφοριών σχετικά με το έργο και την πρόοδο των δραστηριοτήτων με την πάροδο του χρόνου. Μηνιαίες ενημερώσεις ειδήσεων, ανασκοπήσεις τύπου, διάδοση για συναντήσεις διαβούλευσης, συνέδρια, ενημερωτικές εκδηλώσεις και περιβαλλοντική εκπαίδευση ήταν μερικές από τις μεθόδους που χρησιμοποιήθηκαν για την εμπλοκή της κοινότητας.

Conservation actions were accompanied by numerous communication, awareness, and engagement activities involving students, residents, tourists, and local operators to raise awareness about the natural heritage and environmental issues of the Abruzzo and Cypriot coasts. Information brochures, leaflets, explanatory panels placed in intervention areas, audiovisual documents (4 clips and 2 documentary), thematic rollup and a periodic newsletter on project activities were produced once a year for a total of 5. Press releases and interviews published by the local media were also conducted. Twenty-one schools were involved with classroom lessons and tours, consistent with restrictions due to the Covid-19 pandemic, involving about 1,500 children. The project's website, available in Italian and English, and its Facebook page served as tools to disseminate information about the project and the progress of activities over time. Monthly news updates, press reviews, dissemination for consultation meetings, conferences, informational events, and environmental education were some of the methods used to engage with the community.

Μελλοντικές προσδοκίες

Future Perspectives

Κοιτάζοντας προς το μέλλον, προγραμματίζεται η συνεχιζόμενη συμμετοχή των πανεπιστημίων στην παρακολούθηση και αξιολόγηση της αποτελεσματικότητας των δράσεων διατήρησης. Επιπλέον, οι τοπικές αρχές που είναι υπεύθυνες για τη συντήρηση των υποδομών θα διαδραματίσουν κρίσιμο ρόλο στην εξασφάλιση της συνέχειας και της επιτυχίας των πρωτοβουλιών προστασίας και της βιώσιμης διαχείρισης των παράκτιων και θαλάσσιων οικοσυστημάτων. Οι ενδιαφερόμενοι φορείς θα κληθούν να συμβάλουν ενεργά με την υποστήριξή τους και τους πόρους τους για να διασφαλιστεί η συντήρηση και η ανάπτυξη των προστατευόμενων περιοχών. Στην Κύπρο, η απομάκρυνση της ακακίας θα επαναληφθεί χρησιμοποιώντας κρατικά κονδύλια. Τέλος, τα περιφερειακά φυτώρια θα συμμετέχουν στην αναπαραγωγή ιθαγενών φυτικών ειδών των παράκτιων οικοσυστημάτων, συμβάλλοντας έτσι στη διατήρηση της τοπικής γενετικής κληρονομιάς. Αυτές οι συνέργειες μεταξύ θεσμικών και ενδιαφερόμενων φορέων, θα είναι ουσιαστικές για τη διασφάλιση της μακροπρόθεσμης επιτυχίας και βιωσιμότητας του έργου LIFE CALLIOPE. Οι δραστηριότητες ευαισθητοποίησης και διάδοσης θα συνεχιστούν τα επόμενα χρόνια.

Looking ahead to the future of the project, there is a planned ongoing involvement of universities in monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness of conservation actions. Additionally, local authorities responsible for maintaining the implemented works will play a crucial role in ensuring the continuity and success of protection initiatives and sustainable management of coastal and marine environments. Stakeholders will be called upon to actively contribute their support and resources to ensure the maintenance and development of protected areas. In Cyprus, the removal of acacia will be repeated using government funds. Finally, regional nurseries will be engaged in propagating native plant species of coastal areas, thus contributing to the preservation of local genetic heritage. These synergies between institutions and stakeholders will be essential to ensure the long-term success and sustainability of the LIFE CALLIOPE project. Outreach and dissemination activities will continue in the years to come.

LIFE CALLIOPE

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COASTAL DUNE HABITATS,
SUBLITTORAL SANDBANK, MARINE REEFS:
CONSERVATION, PROTECTION, AND THREATS MITIGATION

UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI
DEL MOLISE

Ανάδοχος Φορέας: Abruzzo Region (Ιταλία)

Συνεργαζόμενοι Φορείς: Τμήμα Περιβάλλοντος - Υπουργείο Γεωργίας, Αγροτικής Ανάπτυξης και Περιβάλλοντος (Κύπρος), University of Molise (Ιταλία), Πανεπιστήμιο Frederick University (Κύπρος), C.I.R.S.P.E. - Italian Center for Research and Studies on Fishing (Ιταλία)

Διάρκεια: 09/2018 - 09/2024

Συνολικός προϋπολογισμός: 1,928,505 Ευρώ

Συγχρηματοδότηση από ΕΕ: 1,157,103 Ευρώ

Coordinator Beneficiary: Abruzzo Region (Italy) **Associated Beneficiaries:** Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development and Environment (Cyprus), University of Molise (Italy), Frederick University (Cyprus), C.I.R.S.P.E. - Italian Center for Research and Studies on Fishing (Italy) **Duration :** 09/2018 - 09/2024 **Total Budget: 1,928,505 Euros EU Contribution: 1,157,103 Euros**

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